

EFFECTS OF RESISTANCE HEATING ELEMENT ON JOINING STRENGTH OF CF/PPS COMPODITES

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to reveal the effects of resistance heating element joining strength of CF/PPS laminates. The contents for evaluation were cross sectional of resistance heating element, electric conducting behavior, surface condition of joint section peeled off after applying current and single lap shear strength. The material for the experiment was woven CF/PPS laminates as joining welding test specimen. The effects of molding temperature when producing heating element, insulating layer and applied current were investigated to obtain the optimum condition for resistance welding. From the experimental results, it is considered that when using a resistance pressure body with increased resin impregnation, leakage from the resistance heating element to the laminate occurs during fusion bonding. In addition, in order to prevent the electrical leakage from the resistance heating element to the laminate, a glass cloth or ceramic fiber paper was inserted into the resistance heating element to perform fusion bonding. As a result, the electric current required for fusion is reduced by the influence of the insulation layer, but the tensile shear strength is reduced by about 30% compared to the resistance heating element without the insulation layer inserted. In the case of the resistance heating element using ceramic fiber paper as the insulating layer, the resistance heating element with high resin impregnation showed higher value than the tensile shear strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) has high performance properties such as high productivity, recyclability and impact resistance compared to thermosetting composites. Therefore, CFRTP has a wide range of applications in aerospace, automotive and industrial products[1]. The joining process is a necessary step to manufacture complex geometry parts and large-scaled structures using CFRTP[2]. The joining of thermoplastic composites can be divided into several methods such as mechanical fastening, adhesive bonding and fusion joining or welding. The mechanical fastening method has some disadvantages such as stress concentrations, gain of weight and so on. Adhesive bonding method is also difficult to bond chemically between thermoplastic polymers. Therefore, the fusion joining or welding is suitable for CFRTP parts. There are several types of fusion joining methods for CFRTP such as ultrasonic welding, resistance welding, induction welding and so on, and these heating principles are completely different. The resistance welding method has several advantages such as simple joining device, cost-effective and in applicability to large structures compared to other fusion joining methods[3-5]. In this method, heating elements such as stainless steel mesh has been inserted between joint surfaces. However, the heating elements are undesirable materials which has disadvantage on recyclability, stress concentration and corrosion resistance because the metallic heating elements remains joining parts. Therefore, the carbon materials as CFRTP are desirable as heating element for resistance welding.

Authors have been proposed the use of carbon fiber heating element to solve these problems. In our previous study, the resistance welding method for CFRTP was developed using spread unidirectional carbon fiber as heating element. As the result, the single lap tensile shear strength increased at least three times compared to using metallic heating elements, because the fusion layer was reinforced by carbon fiber heating elements. However, in the case of using spread carbon fiber as heating element,

the temperature distribution was uneven frequently, because it was difficult to place uniformly the carbon fibers. Therefore, it is not suitable for welding of large scaled structures. Thus, in order to solve these problems, woven carbon fiber was used as heating element in this study.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND CONDITIONS

2.1 MATERIARS

The materials used for the experiment is CF/PPS laminate (TenCate, CETEX[®], CF/PPS) as shown in Figure 1(a). This laminate has 5H sateen weave construction with a resin content of $V_f=45\text{vol.}\%$ and a thickness of $t=1.2\text{mm}$. The PPS resin is semi-crystalline polymer. The result of differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) analysis shown that the glass-transition temperature is $T_g=90^\circ\text{C}$, and the melting temperature is $T_m=290^\circ\text{C}$. The result of thermogravimetric analysis (TG) also shown that the decomposition temperature is $T_d=410^\circ\text{C}$.

The material of resistance heating element is plain weave carbon fiber sheets (Toray Industries, Inc., 3k plain weave, woven-CF), PPS film (Toray Industries, Inc., Torelina[®]), and micro glass cloth (featherfield Co., Ltd., N1213500), ceramic fiber paper (SAKAGUCHI E.H VOC CORP., BSFP300) as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Material used for experiments.

2.2 MANUFACTURING METHOD OF HEATING ELEMENT

Figure 2 shows the method of manufacturing resistance heating element. Woven-CF sheets were inserted between two PPS films, and then these materials was molded by hot press. In this study, in order to investigate the effect of the polymer impregnation property of the resistance heating element on the resistance welding, PPS film was used for the preparation of the resistance heating element, the heating temperature of the mold (t_{mold}) was changed and electrical fusion splicing was performed. Figure 2 (b) shows a method of preparing a resistive heating element in which glass cloth, ceramic fiber paper are inserted in the insulating layer as a measure to prevent electrical leakage from the resistive heating element to the laminate during electrical adhesion.

(a) without insulating layer

(b) with insulating layer

Figure 2: Method of manufacturing resistance heating element

2.3 RESISTANCE WELDING METHOD

Figure 3 shows the appearance of resistance welding method using spread-CF or woven-CF heating element. The resistance heating element was inserted between the two woven CF/PPS laminates for fusion bonding, and the pressure was pressurized with $P=6$ MPa through the heat insulating material. The copper electrode was pressed with a constant load on the carbon fiber exposed at both ends of the resistance heating element. The test specimen was clipped by insulating plates made of ceramics. As the superimposed voltage controlled by an DC power supply (Kikusui electronics Co., Ltd., PWR800L) was applied to carbon fiber heating elements. Then, joule heat occurred in the joint interface between laminates, and thus the PPS polymer was melted around the resistance heating element. In this study, the effect of the width W and length L of the fused part of the woven CF/PPS laminates on the fusion bonding behavior was investigated under the various welding conditions shown in table 1.

Figure 3: Schematic drawing of resistance welding method

Table 1: Experimental conditions of resistance welding.

Applied current, I [A]	0~12
Conducting time, t [s]	300
Load, P [MPa]	1
insulating layer	none, grass cloth, ceramic fiber paper

2.4 EVALUATION METHOD

The images of joint surfaces peeled off after joining were imported with a scanner device (Epson Co., Ltd., ES-7000H), and the welding area (A_w) was obtained by image analysis. The single lap shear

strength test was carried out to evaluate a joint strength by using universal testing machine (Shimadzu Co., Ltd., AG-50kN XDplus). Fig.4 shows the appearance of single lap joining test specimen. Before single lap shear strength testing, Al tabs were bonded to end of specimens with epoxy adhesive.

Figure 4: Geometry of single lap joining test specimen.

The cross-head speed was $v=1\text{mm/min}$. The LSS was calculated by using this equation (1)

$$\tau_{ap} = \frac{P}{A_L} \quad (1)$$

where τ_{ap} , tensile shear strength [kN]; A_L , overlap area [mm^2] and P , maximum tensile force

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 5 shows the cross-sectional image of the resistance heating element ($t_{mold}=280^\circ\text{C}$). From this result, PPS polymer was not impregnated into fiber of resistance heating element. It is considered that the melt viscosity of PPS polymer was not decreased sufficiently. Fig.4 shows the cross-sectional image of the resistance heating element ($t_{mold}=310^\circ\text{C}$). It was confirmed that polymer is impregnated between fibers. It was considered that the polymer melted and impregnated between the fibers by increasing the heating temperature of the mold.

Figure 5: Resistance heating element ($t_{mold}=280^\circ\text{C}$)

Figure 6 shows effects of temperature of the mold on single lap shear strength. The applied current was $I=12\text{A}$. The single lap shear strength was 26% higher for $t_{mold}=280^\circ\text{C}$ than for $t_{mold}=310^\circ\text{C}$. This is because the polymer layer of the resistance heating element of $t_{mold}=310^\circ\text{C}$ was thin and electric leak occurred to the CF/PPS laminate during welding.

Figure 7 is peeled surface of the specimen using the resistance heating element of $t_{mold}=280^\circ\text{C}$ and $t_{mold}=310^\circ\text{C}$. (b) has more polymer in carbon fiber than in (a). It is thought that this is due to the fact that the resistance heating element of (b) was previously impregnated with polymer.

From the results, when polymer was previously impregnated in the resistance heating element, the carbon fiber of peeled surface was impregnated with polymer but the single lap shear strength decreased. It is thought that it is important to prevent electric leakage from the resistance heating element to the CF/PPS laminates.

Figure 6: Effects of temperature of the mold on single lap shear strength

Figure 7: Peeled surface of the specimen

In order to prevent leakage from the resistive heating element to the laminate, the insulating layer was inserted into the resistive heating element and fusion bonding was performed. The insulating layer used in the experiment is glass cloth or ceramic fiber paper. The insulation layer was inserted into the resistance heating element and fusion bonding was performed. The preparation conditions of each resistance heating element are shown in Table 2.

Figure 7 (a) glass cloth was used. Figure 7 (b) ceramics fiber paper was used. In addition, Figure 7 shows a cross-sectional SEM image of the resistance heating element. From Figure 7, in case of using ceramic fiber paper, it was found that the boundary of (a) between the insulating layer and the resin layer was clearer compared to (b), and the polymer was not so much impregnated into the carbon fiber and the insulating layer.

Table 2: Manufacturing condition of heating element

Mold temperature, t_{mold} [°C]	310
Mold pressure, P_{mold} [MPa]	0~2
Holding time, t_h [min]	10
insulating layer	grass cloth, ceramic fiber paper

Figure 7 : Resistance heating element with insulating layer

A tensile shear test was performed after fusion bonding using a resistance heating element in which a glass cloth was inserted in the insulating layer. Figure 8 shows peeled face, CF/PPS surface and SEM image of peeled face. Carbon fibers appeared at $I=9, 10\text{A}$. The glass cloth appeared and the CF/PPS laminate was severely deformed at $I=11\text{A}$. It is considered that excess current flowed to resistance heating element

Figure 8 : Peeled face, CF/PPS surface and SEM image of peeled face

A tensile shear test was performed after fusion bonding using a resistive heating element in which a ceramic fiber paper ($P_{mold}=1\text{MPa}$) was inserted in the insulating layer. Figure 9 shows peeled face, CF/PPS surface and SEM image of peeled face. Carbon fibers appeared and were dry at $I=9, 10\text{A}$. There was not much impregnation of polymer in carbon fiber. This is considered that the resistance heating element was not impregnated with polymer. The ceramic fiber paper appeared and the CF/PPS laminate was severely deformed at $I=11\text{A}$. It is considered that excess current flowed to resistance heating element.

	Applied current, I [A]		
	9	10	11
Peeled face	<p>Carbon fiber</p>		
CF/PPS surface			
SEM image of peeled face	<p>Carbon fiber</p>		

Figure 9 : Peeled face , CF/PPS surface and SEM image of peeled face

A tensile shear test was performed after fusion bonding using a resistive heating element in which a ceramic fiber paper ($P_{mold}=2\text{MPa}$) was inserted in the insulating layer. Figure 10 shows peeled face, CF/PPS surface and SEM image of peeled face. Carbon fibers and ceramic fiber paper appeared at $I=9, 10\text{A}$. The ceramic fiber paper appeared and the CF/PPS laminate was severely deformed at $I=11\text{A}$. It is considered that the polymer impregnation of the resistance heating element being high.

Figure 10 : Peeled face , CF/PPS surface and SEM image of peeled face

Figure 11 shows effects of insulating layer and applied current on single lap shear strength. In this figure the tensile shear strength decreased at $I=11A$ for any resistance heating element. It is considered that excessive current flows to the resistance heating element due to the insertion of the insulating layer, resulting in overheating. When ceramic fiber paper was used for the insulating layer, tensile shear strength was higher when molding pressure is higher. From this, it is thought that it is better to impregnate resin with CF or an insulating layer at the time of resistance heating element production. From this, it is considered better to impregnate the polymer for resistance heating element.

Figure 11 : Effects of insulating layer and applied current on single lap shear strength

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the influence of resistance heating elements on resistance fusion bonding of CF/PPS laminates was investigated. As a result of performing fusion bonding by changing the preparation conditions of the resistance heating element, the polymer impregnation property of the resistance heating element is increased by raising the molding temperature at the time of manufacturing the resistance heating element, but the tensile shear strength of the test piece after fusion was found to go down. This is considered to be due to the occurrence of electrical leakage from the resistance heating element to the laminate at the time of fusion bonding. In addition, in order to prevent the electrical leakage from the resistance heating element to the laminate, a glass cloth or ceramic fiber paper was inserted into the resistance heating element to perform fusion bonding. As a result, the electric current required for fusion is reduced by the influence of the insulation layer, but the tensile shear strength is reduced by about 30% compared to the resistance heating element without the insulation layer inserted. In the case of the resistance heating element using ceramic fiber paper as the insulating layer, the resistance heating element with high resin impregnation showed higher value than the tensile shear strength.

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